

Learners' Preparation as Perceived by Parents in Laak Davao De Oro

Jim R. Marimon

Abstract. This study investigates the extent of parental preparation for basic education and the level of learners' readiness in Laak North District. The research focuses on the perspectives of teachers and parents, exploring the preparation in terms of skills, knowledge, and values, as well as assessing children's readiness in various developmental areas. The study employs a descriptive research design with both quantitative and qualitative approaches, using a researcher-developed questionnaire and the School Readiness Assessment (SReA). The participants include parents of grade one students from six elementary schools in the district. The findings reveal a high parental commitment to imparting basic education, with a notable emphasis on values. However, teachers rate children as not ready in certain knowledge-based areas. Gender differences in parental preparation are significant, while age and educational attainment show comparable levels of preparation. School-based variations impact the readiness of children. Interviews highlight the collaborative efforts of teachers and parents in preparing children for basic education.

KEY WORDS

1. Basic education 2. parental preparation 3. learners' readiness

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1. Introduction

School readiness is a multifaceted construct encompassing social, emotional, cognitive, linguistic, and self-care domains essential for children's successful transition into formal education (Öngören, 2021). These competencies enable young learners to meet academic expectations, navigate peer interactions, and develop a sense of responsibility within the school environment. While existing literature underscores the role of parents in cultivating these domains through social engagement, emotional support, language development, and behavioral modeling, gaps remain in understanding how these practices vary across socio-economic and cultural contexts (Öngören, 2021). Particularly, there is a lack of longitudinal studies that evaluate the long-term effectiveness of parental practices on sustained academic and developmental outcomes. Another pressing issue influencing school readiness is the growing prevalence of early childhood screen-time. In a study conducted in Kakamega County, Kenya, Okenwa-Vincent et al. (2025) found that children who exceeded the recommended daily screen time of one hour had 52% lower social development scores. Social development also plays a critical role in early education, particularly in fostering communication, behavioral adaptation, and a sense of belonging. Ivakh et al.

(2023) emphasized that effective socialization in preschoolers depends on the synergy between families and educational institutions. Despite this, many children continue to struggle with issues such as poor peer relationships, conflict resolution, and underdeveloped self-concept. These findings point to a research gap in the implementation and evaluation of psychosocial interventions that support both children and caregivers in addressing these socialization barriers. Structured early learning programs have been shown to facilitate social competence. Marshyt-ska et al. (2018) proposed strategies such as integrated lessons, intellectual-speech exercises, and creative games to promote interpersonal skills among senior preschoolers. While their study demonstrated positive outcomes, questions remain about the scalability and cultural adaptability of such interventions, especially in underserved or rural areas. The importance of early assessment is further supported by Tinampay (2019), whose action research validated the effectiveness of the School Readiness Year-End Assessment (SReYA) tool in determining the preparedness of kindergarten pupils in the Philippines. Although the tool proved useful for teachers in identifying developmental needs, its predictive validity for long-term academic success remains unexplored. Similarly, Bulilan et al. (2019) found that older kindergarten entrants exhibited higher academic performance than their younger peers. This raises concerns about equitable access to schooling and highlights the need for systematic, developmentally appropriate readiness assessments. A broader study by Doctor and Macalisang (2024) involving 227 kindergarten learners revealed that self-help skills were the most developed domain, while receptive and expressive language skills lagged significantly. This suggests an urgent need for targeted language interventions and highlights a broader gap in understanding how home language environments and instructional quality influence linguistic development. Pol-

icy frameworks also reflect the critical importance of readiness. DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2006 allows the early admission of children under six, provided they meet the standards of the School Readiness Assessment Tool (Department of Education [DepEd], 2006). However, the implementation of this policy across diverse educational settings, especially those with high student-teacher ratios, has not been sufficiently evaluated. In the Laak North District, despite the implementation of an eight-week Early Childhood Development (ECD) program, recent assessments showed that many Grade 1 pupils remain unprepared for school. This persistent issue underscores a significant research gap in the alignment between ECD curriculum and actual school demands, as well as in understanding the role of parental and institutional support in sustaining readiness gains. Given these challenges, it becomes imperative to investigate the underlying factors influencing school readiness and to design targeted, evidence-based interventions. By addressing the current gaps in research particularly in content engagement, language development, psychosocial support, and policy implementation stakeholders can more effectively support children's holistic development and ensure a smoother transition into formal education.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This investigation is anchored on Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, serving as a foundational framework for comprehending the intricate interplay of factors shaping a child's educational development and readiness. The relevance of this theory is paramount, as understanding learners' readiness involves recognizing that a child's educational journey is not isolated but deeply embedded within a network of interacting systems, echoing Bronfenbrenner's ecological perspective. Moreover, Vygotsky's theory underscores the importance of the sociocultural environment in shaping a child's readiness for formal education. The

Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is particularly pertinent, representing the gap between a child's current development level and their potential level of development with guidance and support. Understanding and leveraging the ZPD is essential for educators and parents to tailor educational strategies and support, ensuring a child is adequately prepared to navigate the challenges of formal schooling. Thus, this theory highlights the collaborative role of parents and teachers in scaffolding a child's learning experiences and readiness. Emphasizing the holistic development of young learners, the theoretical framework that underpins this study finds resonance in the Developmental Milestones Theory, an established paradigm within the realm of child development, directing its focus toward essential facets of growth. These facets encompass gross and fine motor skills, receptive and expressive language abilities, and cognitive and socio-emotional aptitudes. Moreover, the theory acknowledges the importance of sensory discrimination and visual motor integration, fundamental components contributing to a child's holistic readiness for formal schooling. Through the lens of this theoretical framework, the study endeavors to validate the Department's objectives by rigorously evaluating the achievement of age-appropriate milestones, thereby substantiating a child's preparedness to engage effectively with the Grade 1 curriculum. This study is one of the major thrusts of the Department of Education to ensure that Grade 1 entrants are ready for different developmental domains such as gross motor, fine motor, receptive and expressive language, cognitive, and socio-emotional domains in support of the goal. The Bureau of Elementary Education developed a Database and Reporting System, formally launched in 2009, to determine the developmental domains in which children need help. The Database Systems for the School Readiness Assessment (SReA) is a set of procedures and software programs developed to

address problems in SReA data processing, reporting, and transmitting/submission of reports, enabling decision-makers at the school, division, region, and national levels to make maximum use of the SReA data/results and support the national implementation of the SReA (DepEd Memorandum No. 417, s. 2010). Based on the presented theories of the study, the researcher will conceptualize the independent variable in this study as the extent of basic education with the following indicators: skills refer to ability and capacity acquired through deliberate, systematic, and sustained effort to smoothly and adaptively carry out complex activities or job functions; knowledge refers to familiarity with someone or something, which can include facts, information, descriptions, and values; and values refer to major influences on a person's behavior and attitude, serving as broad guidelines in all situations. The dependent variable is the learner's readiness of students with the following indicators: gross motor refers to movements that involve large muscle groups and are generally broader and more energetic; fine motor refers to movements that require a high degree of control and precision; receptive language means the ability to listen and understand language, while expressive language is the ability to communicate with others using language; sensory discrimination and serration/classification refer to the ability to correctly register or recognize sensory input on a neurological level in order to use it functionally. Concept formation refers to a learning task in which a human or machine learner is trained to classify objects by being shown a set of example objects along with their class labels; numeracy refers to the ability to reason and to apply simple numerical concepts; reading readiness refers to the point at which a person is ready to learn to read and the time during which a person transitions from being a non-reader into a reader; and construction and visual integration refer to eye-hand coordination and are required for tasks such as writ-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

ing and copying material, handwriting/cursive, drawing, pencil-paper tasks, copying from the board, and

2. Methodology

This chapter outlined the methodology employed in conducting the study, including the research design, participants, data-gathering instruments, and statistical tools used in analyzing the data.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a quantitative research approach using a descriptive-correlational design to investigate the extent of parental preparation in the areas of values, knowledge, and skills, and how these related to or predicted the level of learners' readiness for formal schooling. As Creswell and Creswell (2018) emphasized, quantitative research is intended to explain, predict, and explore relationships among variables, describe current conditions, and evaluate the influence of specific factors on targeted outcomes. The descriptive component of this study was used to systematically examine and interpret existing parental practices in early childhood preparation, as well as the developmental readiness of learners across multiple domains such as motor skills, language, cognitive abilities, and social-emotional development (Mertler Charles, 2018). In addition, the correlational design

allowed the researcher to examine the statistical relationships between the independent variables—specifically, the extent of basic education preparation done by parents (in terms of skills, knowledge, and values), along with demographic factors such as gender, age, and educational attainment—and the dependent variable, which was the learners' level of readiness. According to Creswell (2018), correlational research provided a framework for measuring the strength and direction of associations between variables, offering valuable insights into how early home-based interventions might have influenced a child's preparedness to engage in formal education.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—This study was conducted with strict adherence to ethical standards as prescribed in institutional and national research guidelines. The researcher ensured that all protocols, especially those concerning participant rights, data protection, and transparency, were met in accordance with approved ethical standards. All research instruments, including the researcher-made questionnaire and related documents, were submitted for review and approval by the designated Ethics Committee. Only upon receiving formal ethical clearance did the researcher proceed with data collection and analysis. *Informed Consent* Prior to participation, all respondents were provided with a written informed consent form. This document outlined the purpose of the study, the scope of participation, the voluntary nature of involvement, and the assurance of confidentiality. The consent process ensured that respondents were fully informed and understood the rationale for the research, empowering them to make a deliberate and unpressured decision regarding their participation. The researcher emphasized that refusal to participate or withdrawal from the study at any time would not result in any form of penalty or disadvantage. The psychological well-being and comfort of all respondents were respected at every stage of the

research process. *Participant Vulnerability* As the respondents in this study were parents and not considered members of a vulnerable population, there was minimal risk of harm or distress. Nonetheless, the researcher ensured that participation was conducted at the convenience of the respondents and in a manner that respected their time and privacy. All necessary efforts were taken to maintain their dignity, autonomy, and confidentiality. *Privacy and Confidentiality* This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher ensured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher ensured that no personal data was shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data was exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey information. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural sources of information. *Risk, Benefits, and Safety* The researcher clearly communicated the objectives, benefits, and nature of the study to the respondents before participation. The study did not pose any physical or psychological risks and avoided collecting any sensitive or personal information unrelated to the research objectives. Survey content was straightforward and non-invasive. Respondents were given adequate time to complete the survey and were informed that they could skip any question that caused discomfort. The researcher prioritized the overall welfare, safety, and autonomy of all participants throughout the study process. *Justice* Equal treatment was afforded to all potential respondents. Participation was based solely on the inclusion criteria, and no respondent was discriminated against or given preferential treat-

ment. Fairness in the selection of participants was upheld to ensure the validity and ethical soundness of the study. After the completion of data gathering, the researcher formally thanked all participants for their valuable time and contributions. Transparency The researcher committed to maintaining honesty and transparency in all research-related procedures and communication. All research activities—including data collection, analysis, and reporting—followed the approved methodology. Participants were clearly informed about the nature and extent of their involvement. Results were presented objectively, without manipulation, and all relevant documentation was retained and made available if needed for verification. Qualification of the Researcher The researcher acknowledged her ethical responsibility to remain competent and knowledgeable throughout the conduct of this study. To uphold the quality and integrity of the research, she actively sought guidance, consulted reliable sources, and applied best practices in educational research. Any potential conflict of interest was avoided, and personal biases did not influence data interpretation or reporting. Adequacy of Facilities All necessary arrangements were made to ensure that respondents could participate in the study without difficulty. For participants completing the survey online, the researcher provided mobile data support if needed. For face-to-face administration, the survey was conducted in a quiet and conducive environment. Data was checked for completeness and accuracy before analysis to minimize errors and ensure the reliability of results. Community Involvement The researcher intended to ensure that the study extended beyond academic fulfillment and contributed meaningfully to the community. Upon completion, the findings were shared with stakeholders in an accessible and educational manner. These results may have served as a basis for further research or were presented at academic conferences to inform public discourse and policy on learner

readiness and parental involvement. Through these efforts, the study aimed to create lasting value and actionable insights for educational community.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study was conducted in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, during the school year 2023–2024. The respondents were the parents of Grade 1 entrants enrolled in six selected elementary schools within the district. A total of 156 parents participated in the study. The respondents were distributed as follows: 30 from Limot Elementary School, 20 from Barubo Elementary School, 30 from Sisimon Elementary School, 28 from Kiokmay Elementary School, 32 from Hinagtungan Elementary School, and 16 from Concepcion Integrated School. The schools and respondents were selected through purposive sampling, ensuring that the data reflected a broad and representative cross-section of the district’s school communities. This approach allowed for meaningful analysis and comparison of the data across different school settings.

2.4. Research Instrument—Two primary research instruments were utilized in this study to gather the necessary data. The first was a researcher-made questionnaire designed to assess the extent of parental preparation for their children’s basic education. This instrument covered three major domains: skills, knowledge, and values. Each item was formulated to reflect specific home-based behaviors or practices that contributed to early learning and development. To ensure the accuracy and appropriateness of the content, the questionnaire underwent validation by the Thesis Committee, which evaluated it for clarity, reliability, and content validity prior to administration. The second instrument was the School Readiness Assessment (SReA), a standardized tool prescribed by the Department of Education. This assessment was administered by Grade 1 teachers and was used to evaluate the learners’ level of readiness

across eight developmental domains: gross motor skills, fine motor skills, receptive and expressive language, sensory discrimination/serration and classification, concept formation, numeracy, reading readiness, and construction/visual motor integration. The SReA served as a diagnostic instrument commonly employed in Philip-

pine schools to guide instructional planning and provide appropriate support to learners at the beginning of the school year.

To measure the extent of basic education done by the parents, the parameter limits used were as follows:

Levels of Learner Readiness

Parameter Limits	Level	Meaning
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	It means that the basic education was very much extensive.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	It means that the basic education was much more extensive.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	It means that the child’s basic education was moderately extensive.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	It means that basic education was less extensive.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	It meant that basic education was not extensive.

Reading Readiness (10 Items)

Parameter Limits	Level	Meaning
7.13–10.00	Ready	This meant that the reading ability of the child passed the reading requirement set under the SReA.
0.00–7.12	Not Ready	This meant that the reading ability of the child did not pass the reading requirement set under the SReA.

Indicator Scores (5 Items)

Parameter Limits	Level	Meaning
3.57–5.00	Ready	This meant that the child passed the specific requirement set under the SReA.
1.00–3.56	Not Ready	This meant that the child did not pass the specific requirement set under the SReA.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—

Total Score (46 Items)

Parameter Limits	Level	Meaning
33.00–46.00	Ready	This meant the child was prepared for the basic education required under the SReA.
0.00–32.99	Not Ready	This meant the child was unprepared for the basic education required under the SReA.

The researcher followed a systematic procedure in conducting the study to ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected. Initially, a researcher-made questionnaire was constructed to measure the extent of basic education preparation done by parents, focusing on three domains: skills, knowledge, and values. This instrument was reviewed by the research adviser and a panel of experts for evaluation and validation. After incorporating suggested revisions, the finalized version of the questionnaire was translated into the local dialect to ensure clarity and comprehension among respondents, particularly those with limited proficiency in English.

Following validation and translation, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the parents of Grade 1 entrants across six selected schools in Laak North District. The distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires were done with care, ensuring that participants were fully informed of the purpose of the study and their rights as respondents. Ethical protocols, including confidentiality, voluntary participation, and data privacy, were strictly observed throughout the data collection process. Upon completion, the responses were tallied, encoded, and prepared for statistical analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis—The data gathered from the validated questionnaires and the School Readiness Assessment (SReA) were subjected to appropriate quantitative statistical treatments to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. The following statistical tools were employed: Percentage This statistical tool was used to determine the distribution of respondents from each participating school. Percentage is a descriptive measure that expresses the frequency of a category in relation to the total population, allowing for a clearer understanding of proportional representations within the dataset. As explained by Frankfort-Nachmias and Leon-Guerrero (2018), it effectively summarizes categorical data and facilitates comparison groups. Mean The mean was employed to identify the average level of parental preparation and the level of learners’ readiness across

the assessed domains. It is a measure of central tendency that summarizes numerical data by computing the average score, helping to identify general trends and compare results across variables (Wagner, 2020). t-Test This inferential statistic was used to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in the extent of parental preparation when respondents were grouped according to gender. It is appropriate for comparing the means of two independent groups to assess whether observed differences are likely due to chance (Choudhary, 2018). Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) ANOVA was applied to assess significant differences in parental preparation and learner readiness when respondents were grouped based on age, educational attainment, and school. This statistical technique compares the means of three or more groups and determines whether any

observed variation is statistically meaningful (Liang, Fu, Wang, 2019). These statistical methods provided a robust framework for in-

terpreting the data and testing the hypotheses, allowing the researcher to draw conclusions that were grounded in empirical evidence.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the study. These are the findings of the problems raised in the previous chapter. They are presented both in textual and tabular forms.

3.1. The Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents in Terms of Skills—Table 1 shows the extent of basic education preparation done by parents in the Laak North District, specifically in terms of skills, knowledge, and values. The overall mean score was 4.16, corresponding to the descriptive level of “Extensive.” This indicates that parents are actively involved in preparing their children for basic education, with consistent efforts noted across all three areas. Among the domains, values had the highest mean score (M = 4.37), interpreted as “Very Extensive.” This suggests that parents place strong emphasis on developing their children’s behavior, discipline, and social-emotional awareness at home. This supports the idea presented in the Review of Significant Literature that early value formation begins in the home and serves as a

crucial element of school readiness, especially in terms of learner behavior and classroom adjustment. In terms of knowledge (M = 4.09) and skills (M = 4.03), both were rated as “Extensive.” These results reflect meaningful efforts by parents to prepare their children cognitively and physically for formal education. This is consistent with Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems Theory, which highlights the family as a critical component of a child’s immediate environment, directly influencing learning, behavior, and development. The home, as child’s first learning space, serves as a foundation for acquiring basic concepts, communication skills, and motor development. These findings address Research Question 1 in the Statement of the Problem, which seeks to assess the extent of parental involvement in the areas of skills, knowledge, and values.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents

No.	Indicators	Mean	Description
1	Skills	4.03	Extensive
2	Knowledge	4.09	Extensive
3	Values	4.37	Very Extensive
Overall		4.16	Extensive

The results demonstrate that parents in the district engage not only in academic preparation (e.g., basic literacy and numeracy) but also in the development of life skills and moral grounding—indicating a holistic approach to early education. In summary, the extensive level of

parental preparation across the three domains reflects a strong and intentional effort by families to equip their children for formal schooling. These results support existing literature emphasizing the importance of home-based support in shaping early learning outcomes and establish-

ing a strong foundation for children’s readiness to learn in school.

3.2. *Level of Child Readiness as Rated by Teachers*—Table 2 presents the assessment of learners’ school readiness as evaluated by teachers using the School Readiness Assessment (SReA) tool prescribed by the Department of Education. The overall mean score of 4.16, interpreted as “Not Ready,” suggests that learners in Laak North District, on average, have not yet met the developmental standards necessary to transition smoothly into formal schooling. Among the eight domains assessed, only three—gross motor (M = 4.19), fine motor (M = 3.77), and receptive/expressive language (M = 3.59)—were rated as “Ready.” These domains relate primarily to physical coordination and basic communication, which indicates that many children demonstrate competence in movement and expressing or understanding language. These strengths may reflect parents’ extensive involvement in physical play and verbal interactions at home, as supported by the earlier finding that parental

preparation in skills and values was “Extensive” or “Very Extensive.” However, the remaining five domains—sensory discrimination/serration (M = 3.33), concept formation (M = 3.35), numeracy (M = 3.41), reading readiness (M = 3.27), and construction/visual integration (M = 3.22)—were rated as “Not Ready.” These areas demand higher-order cognitive abilities such as logical thinking, pattern recognition, early math, and symbolic literacy. Despite strong parental support in values and daily routines, these more academic-related competencies appear underdeveloped. This aligns with the literature discussed in the RSL, particularly the idea that readiness is multifaceted, encompassing not only social and physical preparedness but also cognitive and conceptual domains. While Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems Theory emphasizes the critical role of the home environment in early development, the results suggest that parental preparation may have been more focused on values and routines than on academic and cognitive stimulation—such as numeracy or early literacy activities.

Table 2. Level of Child Readiness as Rated by Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Description
1	Gross Motor	4.19	Ready
2	Fine Motor	3.77	Ready
3	Receptive/Expressive Language	3.59	Ready
4	Sensory Discrimination/Serration	3.33	Not Ready
5	Concept Formation	3.35	Not Ready
6	Numeracy	3.41	Not Ready
7	Reading Readiness	6.72	Not Ready
8	Construction/Visual Motor Integration	3.22	Not Ready
Overall		4.16	Not Ready

These findings address Research Question 2 in the Statement of the Problem, which inquires into learners’ readiness across specific domains. The results indicate that while certain

developmental aspects are progressing well, a significant portion of learners remain underprepared for the academic expectations of formal schooling. In conclusion, the mismatch between

extensive parental involvement and the limited readiness in academic domains highlights a gap that requires more targeted support. Schools and communities may need to strengthen early learning programs, conduct parent orientations, and provide learning materials that bridge home practices with formal school readiness indicators. Greater synergy between home preparation and school-based expectations can enhance the overall readiness and long-term academic success of learners in the district.

3.3. *Differences in the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents when Respondents*

Table 3. Differences in the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents when Respondents are Grouped According to Gender

Gender of Parents	Mean	F-value (Computed)	F-value (Tabular)	Decision
Male	3.95	2*2.83	2*1.96	2*Ho Rejected
Female	4.32			

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

This finding reflects longstanding patterns of gendered parental roles in early education. In the context of Filipino households, mothers are traditionally more involved in the educational and developmental preparation of children, particularly in basic education (Basiao, 2024). This maternal involvement is often associated with routines that foster academic and socio-emotional readiness, including structured play, communication skills, and responsive caregiving—key domains identified in readiness frameworks. Supporting this, Susanti et al. (2023) observed that parents generally aim to prepare their children academically, but it is often the mother who complements this with a focus on values formation and emotional preparedness. This dual focus enhances a child’s adaptability to formal schooling environments, especially in early grades. Meanwhile, Parke and Cookston (2019) noted that while fathers con-

are Grouped According to Gender —Table 4 presents the differences in the extent of basic education preparation done by parents when grouped according to gender. Female parents had a higher mean score (M = 4.32) than male parents (M = 3.95). The computed t-value (2.83) is greater than the tabular value (1.96) at the 0.05 significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a statistically significant difference in the extent of basic education done by parents based on gender.

tribute meaningfully—particularly to physical development and socio-emotional skills—their participation is often less visible or consistent, due in part to societal expectations and work-related constraints. Cultural beliefs and traditional parenting models still often position mothers as the primary caregivers, which may account for the higher reported involvement by female respondents. Moreover, Cabrera, Volling, and Barr (2018) argue that dominant models of learner readiness have long centered on maternal engagement, inadvertently overlooking the evolving roles of fathers. This study reinforces that observation, as paternal involvement—while present—is reported at a lower level. In some cultural contexts, readiness may be defined differently by fathers and mothers. Lin and Yang (2024) highlighted that parental beliefs and practices vary according to cultural and individual expectations, often influencing

how parents prioritize aspects of early learning. Female respondents in this study may have aligned their preparation practices more closely with the school's perceived expectations, leading to higher readiness scores. These findings point to the importance of encouraging more inclusive and balanced parental participation in readiness efforts. While mothers are traditionally more involved, empowering fathers to participate equally could enrich the child's early learning experience and provide a more holistic foundation for formal schooling.

3.4. Difference in the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents when Respondents are Grouped According to Age of Parents—Table 7 presented the differences in the extent of basic education preparation done by parents when grouped according to their age. The highest mean scores were observed in the youngest (18–27 years old) and oldest (58 and above) age groups, both with a mean of 4.28. Meanwhile, the lowest mean (3.94) was recorded in the 48–57 age group. Despite these variations, the results of the one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed that the computed F-value of 1.12 was less than the tabular F-value of 2.42 at the 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there was no significant difference in the extent of preparation done by parents across different age groups. The findings show no significant difference in basic education preparation among parents across age groups ($F(4, N) = 1.12, p > 0.05$). Both the youngest (18–27 years) and oldest (58 and above) parents had similarly high engagement, while middle-aged groups were slightly lower but comparable. This suggests

3.5. Difference in the Extent of Basic Education done by Parents when Respondents are Grouped According to Educational Attainment of Parents—Table 5 presented the differences in the extent of basic education preparation done

parental involvement in foundational learning is consistent regardless of age. This aligns with research indicating that parental involvement depends more on beliefs, values, and knowledge about child development than on demographic factors. Within the basic education framework, which includes literacy, numeracy, and socio-emotional development as required by Philippine law (Republic Act No. 10968), effective parental participation is crucial—especially amid challenges like curriculum misalignment (Abejuela et al., 2023) and pandemic-related remote learning. The results imply that efforts to improve parental preparation should focus on enhancing self-efficacy and awareness rather than targeting age groups (Kong Yasmin, 2022). From the learner readiness perspective, parental support across cognitive, socio-emotional, and motor domains is key to a child's school preparedness (Putcha et al.). Since parents across ages showed similar engagement, readiness appears linked more to support quality than parental age. However, as noted by Susanti et al. (2023), academic skills often receive more emphasis than socio-emotional development, highlighting the need for holistic parent education. Overall, parental involvement in skills, knowledge, and values remains consistent across ages, reflecting internal motivators like beliefs and self-efficacy (Kong Yasmin, 2022; Outhwaite Melhuish, 2025). This underscores the need for inclusive, culturally responsive parenting programs that support all parents and align with calls for equitable, quality basic education from global organizations like UNESCO and the World Bank.

by parents when grouped according to their educational attainment. The data revealed that high school graduates reported the highest mean of 4.28, while elementary graduates recorded the lowest mean of 3.99. Interestingly, elementary

Table 4. Difference in the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents when Respondents are Grouped According to Age of Parents

Age of Parents	Mean	F-value (Computed)	F-value (Tabular)	Decision
18 – 27	4.28	6*1.12	6*2.42	6*Ho Accepted
28 – 37	4.14			
38 – 47	4.20			
48 – 57	3.94			
58 and above	3.94			

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

level respondents reported the highest individual mean of 4.97, which may have reflected heightened involvement despite lower formal education. To determine whether these differences were statistically significant, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at the 0.05 level of significance was applied. Results showed a computed F-value of 1.26, which was lower than the tabular F-value of 2.26. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, indicating that there was no significant difference in the extent of preparation done by parents based on their educational attainment. This implied that parents, regardless of academic background, exhibited similar levels of involvement in supporting basic education. Supporting this, Lin and Yang (2024) emphasized that parental engagement was shaped

more by beliefs and cultural values than formal schooling. Their cultural mismatch theory highlighted how differences between school expectations and family cultural practices, especially among Asian immigrant parents, could hinder involvement. These findings suggested that schools should foster culturally responsive environments that validated diverse parenting styles and encouraged inclusive parental participation. Overall, parents from various educational backgrounds demonstrated comparable commitment to their children’s school readiness, underscoring the need to value all parents as partners and to focus parenting programs on enhancing skills and awareness rather than educational level.

Table 5. Difference in the Extent of Basic Education Done by Parents when Respondents Are Grouped According to Educational Attainment of Parents

Educational Attainment of Parents	Mean	F-value (Computed)	F-value (Tabular)	Decision
College Graduate	4.21	6*1.26	6*2.26	6*Ho Accepted
College Level	4.07			
High School Graduate	4.28			
High School Level	4.18			
Elementary Graduate	3.99			
Elementary Level	4.97			

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

3.6. *Difference in the Level of Child Readiness as Rated by Teachers when Respondents are Grouped According to School* —Table 6 presented the difference in the level of child readiness as rated by teachers when respondents were grouped according to school. The data revealed varying mean scores among schools, with Barubo Elementary School obtaining the highest mean of 35.19, followed by Hinagtungan Elementary School (35.02), Sisimon Elementary School (33.47), and Kiokmay Elementary School (33.12).

Limot Elementary School and Concepcion Integrated School reported the lowest means, at 30.68 and 30.75 respectively. To determine whether these variations were statistically significant, the researcher employed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 0.05 level of significance. The computed F-value of 40.12 exceeded the tabular value of 2.27, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This confirmed that there was a significant difference in the level of child readiness across the different schools. The findings implied that the level of child readiness, as perceived by teachers, was not uniform and

was influenced by the school context. This supported the idea that school-specific factors, such as available resources, teacher preparation, and community engagement, could greatly affect early learning outcomes (UNESCO, 2021). Additionally, as highlighted by Adair et al. (2021), disparities in early childhood education quality across different geographic or institutional settings contributed to uneven school readiness levels among children. The higher readiness scores observed in schools like Barubo Elementary may have reflected stronger home-school collaboration, better access to early learning programs, or more consistent instructional practices. This result underscored the need for targeted interventions to ensure equitable readiness development across schools. The Department of Education and local education units might have considered prioritizing support for schools with lower readiness ratings through enhanced parental engagement programs, teacher training, and early learning resource provision, in line with recommendations by the World Bank (2020) on improving foundational learning outcomes through contextualized and data-informed strategies.

Table 6. Difference in the Level of Child Readiness as Rated by Teachers when Respondents Are Grouped According to School

School	Mean	F-value (Computed)	F-value (Tabular)	Decision
Limot Elementary School	30.68	6*40.12	6*2.27	6*Ho Rejected
Barubo Elementary School	35.19			
Sisimon Elementary School	33.47			
Kiokmay Elementary School	35.02			
Hinagtungan Elementary School	33.12			
Concepcion Integrated School	30.75			

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this section, the researcher provided the conclusions and recommendations of the study. The discussion was substantiated by the literature reviewed in the earlier chapters, and the conclusions aligned with the problem statements articulated in this study.

4.1. Findings—The findings of the study revealed that parents in Laak North District are extensively involved in the early education of their children, particularly in the domains of skills, knowledge, and values. In terms of skills development, the overall mean suggests that parents actively engage their children in practical, hands-on activities that promote self-help and motor coordination. Common practices included teaching children to pick up their clothes, participate in household chores, and engage in drawing or writing tasks. These activities are foundational to school readiness, particularly in developing fine and gross motor abilities (Doctor Macalisang, 2024). Such home-based engagements align with global recommendations for early childhood education that emphasize the development of physical and creative skills alongside academic learning (OECD, 2019; UNESCO, 2021). Parental involvement in knowledge-building activities was also found to be extensive. Parents frequently engaged in teaching their children the alphabet, numbers, and basic personal information. These efforts contribute significantly to early literacy and numeracy development, equipping children with the basic academic tools required in formal schooling environments. Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory underscores the importance of guided learning and interaction within the child's immediate environment, particularly the family, in developing higher cognitive functions. Similarly, Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological systems theory identifies the home as a critical influence in shaping a child's educational experiences and readiness. The study's findings reinforce these theories by showing that parental support in early academic tasks lays a crucial foundation for school readiness. Among the three domains, the highest level of parental involvement was observed in values education. Parents emphasized the teaching of polite expressions, respect for elders, daily affection, and discipline. These practices are integral to the development of socio-emotional competence, which is a key component of school readiness according to Bandura's (1986) social learning theory. Bandura posits that children learn behaviors and social norms primarily through observation and imitation of significant adults, particularly parents. Furthermore, UNICEF (2022) advocates for the integration of socio-emotional development in early childhood education, recognizing that emotional regulation, respect for others, and empathy are just as important as academic skills in a child's readiness for school. These findings suggest that in the Laak North District, parents play an essential role in instilling values that prepare children for social interaction and emotional adjustment in the classroom. Despite this strong parental involvement, the assessment of learners' readiness by teachers revealed that the children, on average, were rated as "not ready" for formal schooling. While gross motor, fine motor, and receptive/expressive language domains were rated as "ready," other domains such as concept formation, sensory discrimination, numeracy, reading readiness, and visual-motor integration were rated as "not ready." This indicates that although parents are effective in developing physical and social competencies, there is a noticeable gap in the cognitive and academic dimensions of readiness. This finding reflects Adair et al.'s (2021) assertion that school readiness is a multifaceted construct encompassing not only physical and

emotional preparedness but also cognitive and academic skills. The disparity between the areas parents focus on and those assessed in school readiness evaluations highlights the need for better alignment between home-based preparation and formal educational expectations. When parental preparation was examined according to gender, a significant difference was found, with female parents reporting a higher level of involvement compared to male parents. This finding is consistent with traditional Filipino cultural norms, where mothers are typically more involved in the care and education of young children (Basiao, 2024). Susanti et al. (2023) noted that while both parents aim to support academic preparation, mothers often focus more on emotional and values education, which contributes to children's adaptability in school settings. Research by Cabrera, Volling, and Barr (2018) also supports this, indicating that while fathers contribute to early development, their involvement tends to be less consistent due to external factors such as work and traditional gender roles. These gendered patterns suggest that increasing father engagement in early childhood education could enhance overall school readiness. In contrast, no significant differences were found in the extent of parental preparation when grouped by age or educational attainment. Parents across all age groups, from the youngest (18–27 years) to the oldest (58 years and above), demonstrated comparable levels of involvement. Similarly, parental engagement was consistent regardless of whether respondents had only elementary education or were college graduates. These results support the conclusions of Kong and Yasmin (2022), who argue that parental engagement is driven more by personal beliefs and a sense of responsibility than by demographic characteristics. Lin and Yang (2024) further explain that cultural values and individual motivations are often more influential than formal education in determining parenting practices. This underscores the potential effectiveness of par-

enting programs that focus on building awareness and confidence rather than targeting demographic subgroups. Significant differences were observed, however, in the level of child readiness when grouped according to school. Schools such as Barubo Elementary and Hinagtungan Elementary recorded higher readiness scores compared to Limot and Concepcion Integrated Schools. This variation, confirmed by an ANOVA result with a computed F-value of 40.12, suggests that school-level factors such as teacher preparedness, access to learning resources, and community engagement play a critical role in shaping learners' readiness (UNESCO, 2021). Adair et al. (2021) highlight that geographic and institutional disparities in early learning services can result in uneven levels of school readiness among children. These findings indicate a need for targeted, school-based interventions that address resource disparities and strengthen collaboration between families and educational institutions to support children's early learning and transition to formal schooling.

4.2. Conclusions—This study investigated the extent of basic education preparation done by parents and the corresponding level of learners' readiness in Laak North District. The findings clearly indicate that parents are extensively involved in preparing their children for formal education, particularly in the areas of skills, knowledge, and values. Among these, values education received the highest level of engagement, reflecting strong parental emphasis on moral development, social behavior, and emotional regulation. Skills and knowledge, while also rated as extensive, were slightly lower, suggesting a more balanced but less intensive focus on cognitive and motor development. Despite this significant parental involvement, the overall assessment of learners' readiness by teachers revealed that many children were still not fully prepared for the academic demands of formal schooling. While physical and communication

domains showed adequate development, critical cognitive areas such as numeracy, concept formation, and reading readiness remained underdeveloped. This disconnect suggests that while parents play a crucial role in foundational learning, their focus may not always align with the formal school readiness standards set by the education system. Furthermore, the study found a significant difference in the extent of parental preparation based on gender, with female parents demonstrating greater involvement than their male counterparts. However, no significant differences were observed when parents were grouped according to age or educational attainment, implying that parental engagement is driven more by personal values and commitment than demographic factors. On the other hand, a significant variation in learners' readiness was found when grouped according to school, pointing to institutional and contextual disparities that may influence early learning outcomes. These findings confirm that while parents in Laak North District are playing an active and commendable role in early education, there remains a critical need to strengthen the alignment between home-based preparation and the expectations of the formal education system. To address the observed gaps in learner readiness—particularly in academic domains—collaborative efforts between schools, parents, and local education authorities are essential. Tailored interventions, parent education programs, and resource support should be prioritized to ensure that every child enters school not only socially and emotionally ready but also cognitively equipped to succeed.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the findings and conclusions drawn from this research, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the alignment between parental preparation and learner readiness, and to address the observed gaps in academic competencies and institutional support: Enhance Parental Awareness and Training Programs Edu-

cation stakeholders, including schools and local education units, should initiate regular parenting seminars and training workshops focused on cognitive and academic readiness. These should include practical strategies for parents to support reading, numeracy, concept formation, and problem-solving skills at home, ensuring that preparation extends beyond values and routine behaviors. Promote Balanced Parental Involvement Schools and community leaders should actively encourage greater father participation in early childhood education. This may include father-focused outreach, parenting groups, or activities that highlight the importance of shared parental roles in developing not just socio-emotional and physical readiness but also academic competencies. Strengthen Home-School Collaboration Teachers and school administrators should establish more consistent two-way communication with parents through home visits, parenting conferences, or learning development checklists. This collaboration will help ensure that parents understand school readiness expectations and can adjust their home practices to better support formal learning goals. Standardize Early Learning Readiness Support Across Schools

Given the significant differences in readiness levels across schools, the Department of Education, in collaboration with district offices, should implement equitable resource allocation and teacher development programs. Schools with lower readiness ratings should be prioritized for support, such as additional instructional materials, play-based learning facilities, and teacher mentoring. Integrate School Readiness Modules into Kindergarten Orientation Programs

Prior to formal Grade One enrollment, schools should implement readiness orientation programs for both learners and their parents. These sessions should include hands-on activities and assessments that introduce academic tasks (e.g., basic reading and counting), allow-

ing early identification and support for children who may be developmentally delayed in specific areas.

Develop Culturally Contextualized Learning Materials

Locally developed and culturally relevant storybooks, number games, and visual learning aids should be distributed to parents, especially in rural or under-resourced communities. These materials can help bridge the gap between values-based and academic learning,

and promote parental engagement even among those with limited formal education. Conduct Follow-up Studies on Longitudinal Readiness Outcomes

Future researchers are encouraged to conduct longitudinal studies that track the academic performance and behavioral development of learners assessed in this study. This can provide deeper insight into the long-term impact of early home-based preparation and inform future readiness interventions.

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